

**EDUCATION OF PATRIOTIC QUALITIES OF STUDENTS OF
PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS**

Abdullayev Komiljon Riskulovich

Tashkent State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7602434>

Abstract: In this article, the integral relationship between the education and upbringing of students of vocational colleges, as well as the educational importance of sciences in educating young people is highlighted.

Key words: education, upbringing, youth, student, educational system, continuity.

In the world community, extensive reforms are being implemented to modernize professional education, train qualified and competitive personnel for the labor market, and involve employers in this process. In the age of intensive digital technologies, the development of opportunities for international cooperation and communication, as well as the expansion of cultural, political, and economic borders, is gaining special relevance and importance for future specialists. Evaluation of the parameters related to the phenomenon of morality, which determine the quality of this system, and their application to the educational process, based on advanced foreign experiences, as well as improving the technology of educating the students of professional educational institutions for patriotic qualities, are gaining special relevance[1].

The competitiveness of specialists in the world depends, first of all, on the level of development of their professional competence. The qualities listed above are among the important factors that determine the effectiveness of the professional activity of specialists in the conditions of the market economy. Also, it is important to educate young people who have their own position in the background of various ideological conflicts in the world, who are studying in professional educational institutions, with high potential, to ensure that they have a sense of national pride and loyalty to their Motherland. Ensuring a high level and quality of personnel training; great attention is being paid to patriotism in the context of the organization of scientific and research work on working with young people in educational institutions, increasing their efficiency, wide implementation of research results in practice, mutual integration of education, science and production.

In our country, socio-pedagogical mechanisms of spiritual and moral upbringing of young people have been developed, and on the basis of them, great attention is paid to educating students to become perfect people in all respects. Also, there

is a need to interpret the training of professionals with an independent civic outlook, to develop such qualities as patriotism, steadfastness, and willfulness in them as a pedagogical phenomenon of urgent importance, and to create methodologies of practical description. In Uzbekistan, the government is required to improve the policy of working with youth, "educate the intellectually developed young generation as a well-rounded person, align the quality of education and its evaluation criteria in educational institutions with international standards, and improve the mechanism of educational work[2].

To be able to actively use such achievements in the preparation of patriotic personnel of young people is not to alienate them from our ancient history, but to bring them closer to it is the demand of the times.

In order to strengthen independence, build a free and prosperous Motherland, a free and prosperous life, the role of literature is extremely important in shaping the ideology of national independence in the minds of soldiers. It is a high human virtue to develop students' thinking, to expand the scope of thinking - the wisdom mentioned in our holy books "Avesta", "Holy Qur'an" and "Hadith", great works of Uzbek literature: "The City of Virtuous People", "Boburnoma", " It is expressed in "Tuziklari of Timur". The heroic struggles of our national heroes such as Tomaris, Shiroq, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, and Amir Temur for the fate of the country, that they were unparalleled heroes, that even their enemies recognized their bravery, and that our country brought up such incomparable heroes, attractively conveyed to today's youth. it is necessary to give

The bravery of our ancestors for the freedom of the Motherland arouses a sense of infinite pride and pride in each of us.

Great historical figures who put the interests of the country, the Motherland and the people above their own interests are in honor of the Motherland and the nation, and their lives have been a school of example for all generations. Their name is the golden page of the annals of the Motherland.

Educating today's youth to be courageous, self-respecting, to be obedient, and to feel that the motherland is superior to everything else is a difficult but honorable task for educators, the public, enterprises, neighborhoods, and, moreover, all state and non-state organizations.

Also, regardless of the seasonal nature of patriotism education, the results will be positive only if it is carried out continuously and consistently[3].

ITALY

SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

International scientific-online conference

ITALY

Patriotism is loyalty to the country, a quality that includes love for it, belonging to one's country, a desire to conscientiously serve the interests of one's country and people, to protect it from all enemies during peace and war.

Abu Rayhan Beruni in his works "Relics of Ancient Peoples", "India", "Mineralogy" and other works emphasizes that a perfect human education is high with moral qualities and directly connects it with the human psyche. This ensures a person's physical health and mental and spiritual wealth.

Beruni attached great importance to moral education. "The work of bringing people to social maturity," the scientist says in his works, "is carried out in the process of introducing high mental and moral standards, which are brought up with the help of science, everywhere"[4].

Beruni requires young people to be compassionate, kind, considerate to people, show kindness to them, help people in need, avoid such qualities as cunning, cunning, injustice, indolence, greed, lack of courage, and the pursuit of wealth. He shows his students the difference between "good" and "evil".

Abu Ali ibn Sina connects moral perfection with the sciences of medicine and psychology, and believes that its basis lies in the spiritual environment in the family and the art of education. The scientist elaborates on this idea in his works "Donishnama", "Medical Laws", "Tadbir al-Manozil" and other works. He believes that "Knowledge should be strengthened with good morals." All the activities and skills of a perfect person. habits, knowledge and aspirations end with the rules of etiquette. Only by avoiding evil can one attain knowledge.

References:

1. Abdullayev K.R. Technologie der bildung von patriotischen qualitäten von studenten von beruflichen bildungseinrichtungen // Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. 2022. - ISSN 2749 0866 Vol.2 Issue 1.5 Pedagogical sciences. -P. 855-858.
2. Abdullayev K.R. Assessment of the Patriotic Qualities of Students of Professional Educational Institutions // ACADEMICIA. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. Vol. 11. Issue 1, January 2021. – P. 89-91.
3. Давыдов В. В. Теория развивающего обучения. – М.: ИНТОР, 1996. 44 с.
4. Djo'rayev R.X. Ta'limda interfaol texnologiyalar. – Toshkent, 2010.

